

PROSUMER CONCEPT: CURRENT STATUS AND POSSIBLE FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

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1.- INTRODUCTION

The concept "prosumer" was coined by A. Toffler, a prominent sociologist and futurist who made interesting predictions about the role of consumers in the economy [1]. The term refers to an individual who is not just a consumer, but also participates actively in the production of products. Due to the advancement of technology and the development of domestic manufacturing tools, prosumers have become important actors in the social and economic sphere. It is necessary to clarify its definition, as it can refer to someone who produces for self-consumption (e.g., electrical energy) or also a professional with expertise in a particular area of consumer use.

In 1986 it was anticipated that with electronic technology the consumer could also become a producer [2]. During the same period, the maker movement has developed as an evolution of Do It Yourself (DIY), moving from bricolage and assembly to creation and manufacturing. It is in this regard that new digital manufacturing tools have enabled prosumers to design and manufacture their own products.

User interest in participating in the creative process is increasing (Figure 1). Consequently, tools have been developed that facilitate their involvement in the design and transformation of products [3]. With the advent of the fourth industrial revolution (Industry 4.0), collaborative technologies have contributed to the transition from linear to circular economies, as well as the development of individualized products that cater to the preferences and needs of consumers.

Fig. 1. Data on prosumer activity in 2023.

2.- CURRENT PROSUMER

It is difficult to identify current prosumers. Its original definition covers makers and designers who self-commission, but also DIY and bricolage enthusiasts. The latter are unaware of their prosumer status. Prosumers are described in this work in order to facilitate their identification.

2.1.- PROFILE AND CHARACTERISTICS

The prosumer profile is constantly evolving to adapt to today's society. Nevertheless, previous studies have identified certain patterns that are common to the prosumer population [4]. It is identified that young men lead maker initiatives. On the other hand, individual processes are more divergent in tool use, while group processes are better organized and more specialized. For successful results, a prosumer must possess a certain level of manual and manufacturing skills.

Advances in communication technologies encourage free software and open source. As a result, prosumers are able to easily share their knowledge and projects. However, the level of innovation of their creations is low [5], as they frequently resort to redesign and

customization. Aiming to generate more active users or desumers (designers + consumers), it is important to encourage the integration of the design process into consumer products.

Prosumers are motivated to meet personal desires and needs (Table 1). This results in self-learning which culminates in the satisfaction of achieving a unique result and the empowerment of the individual [6]. This satisfaction, however, is not only due to the final product, but also to the process, which is influenced by factors such as the amount of time, effort, and money invested. As a result, the consumer becomes more emotionally attached to the product.

	Limitations	Drivers
Motivation	Skepticism and frustration. Isolation and loneliness.	Possibility of sharing results. Recognition by other prosumers. Personal satisfaction. Crowdsourcing o crowdfunding.
Knowledge /skills	Lack of experience. Difficulty finding specific resources. Start at a high level.	Free courses, tutorials and guides. Development of STEAM skills in basic and regulated education. Material shared by the community.
Opportunities	Lack of economic resources. Homologation/certification. Loss of guarantees and insurance on modified products.	Intellectual property registration. Options for creating open resources. Start of activity through start-up. Facilitate access to knowledge.

Tabla 1. Characteristics and motivations that define the prosumer

The prosumer is a modern artisan who integrates current technologies and tools for the enjoyment of an alternative to mass manufacturing. This involves the application of technical skills and personal criteria to create a good. These factors characterize prosumers by their participation, commitment and creativity.

It is identified that the prosumer can play the role of external collaborator with the business sector to satisfy their consumption needs. This is done by sharing knowledge and participating in the product design and production. As a result of a more professional profile, the company will be able to create value more effectively [7].

Depending on the level of participation, different types of consumers can be identified. Figure 2 presents a classification that defines each type and analyzes its involvement in the product or service. This includes information on whether it is done individually or collectively, or encompasses design and manufacturing. Finally, each type of prosumer is exemplified by a specific case.

	TYPE	Nº	INTERVENTION	DES / MAN	ACTIONS	EXAMPLES
				<small>Design/Manufact.</small>		
LEVEL OF INTERVENTION	Self-consumption		Total. Generate raw materials	✓ ✓	Build from scratch with own resources	Resource production <i>Power generator, garden</i>
	Professional		Very high. Everything at an expert level	✓ ~	Design and develop the product on request	Co-creation with company <i>Design of a coffee maker</i>
	Maker / DIY		High. Ideation, design and manufacturing	~ ✓	Alter, modify and manufacture own parts	Experimental design <i>3D printed lamp</i>
	Active user or designer user		Medium. Ideation, design and/or manufacturing	~ ~	Adjust and adapt Manufacture own parts	Custom design <i>IKEA hacks</i>
	Mass customization		Low. Design selection only (aesthetic/formal)	~ ✗	Filtering options or selecting features	Aesthetic design and finishes <i>Setting up a car</i>
	Service consumer		Low. They are part of the self-service	✗ ✗	Perform part of the service themselves	Self-service <i>Laundry, Click & Collect</i>
	Usual consumer		Null. Limited to purchase	✗ ✗	Just buy and consume the product.	Consumer products <i>Television, washing machine</i>

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Fig. 2. Classification of prosumers according to their type of intervention on the product.

2.2.- TECHNOLOGICAL

Advances in domestic manufacturing are opening access to a range of knowledge and tools previously only available to few. At both a tangible (3D printing) and intangible (resource platforms) level, global access to communication and information has contributed to a large number of consumers acquiring knowledge in design and manufacturing. These changes offer competitive advantages for open-minded organizations. In addition, they facilitate the creation and transformation of products through the manufacture of their own parts. They not only have the ability to design original products, but also repair existing components. Similarly, another application would be updated by adding new features or improving its functionality.

2.3.- SOCIAL

The activity of the prosumer not only responds to a hobby but also to a need of the current consumer which leads to the creation of communities. These users are interested in changing their consumption habits, like hackers, who seek to give a second life to products or experiment with novel functionalities. If we focus on the maker trend, we often find that their projects are directed at third parties to respond to two objectives: the first, to cover the needs of an individual or group for whom the products on the market are not fully functional; and, the second, to respond to a new need that affects a large part of society and that did not exist or had not been previously detected, as in the Covid-19 period.

2.4.- SUSTAINABILITY

As a community, makers share a desire to raise environmental awareness. One of its objectives is to organize to offer more suitable alternatives to problems neglected by current markets. On the other hand, the prosumer's activity includes the repair, updating and adaptation of the product. This contributes to sustainable development by prolonging its life cycle while reducing resource consumption. Other actions, such as personalization, achieve the same effect thanks to the attachment developed for a unique and personal object. This slows down replenishment, minimizing environmental impact. The same happens with reuse and recycling activities. These RE-DIY trends with the participation of design can be elements of innovation in potentially sustainable practices [8].

2.5.- INNOVATION AND CREATIVE PROCESS

Prosumers are assuming an important role as innovative users in product design and, therefore, as agents of change [9]. They actively innovate in order to create new products rather than restricting themselves to consumption. They seek their own benefit, with no intention of selling later. Innovation arises from constant trial and error when testing your products. In this way, they participate in design and innovation, and can contract production and material resources.

End users' creative processes have proven to be more effective than those driven by companies, since they are based on their needs (Figure 3). Innovation motivation is not due to financial compensation, but rather to their daily experience. The process can vary depending on the degree of participation and the stage in which it acts, whether conceptualization, development or commercialization. It is at the beginning that the greatest innovation is contributed when new ideas and concepts are generated.

Fig. 3. Comparison between the innovation adopted by a prosumer and a company.

3.- EVOLUTIONARY CHALLENGE

Consumers of today, tired of traditional consumption models, seek a new way of interacting with products and services on the market. Likewise, prosumers have found a variety of ways to address these limitations: either acting independently, supported by tools such as tutorials, or by participating in groups where their innovations are shared. As a result of this reality, together with technological advancements, an increasing number of innovative users are able to create value.

From a futuristic perspective, we can see that design, production, and consumption will become unified. It is expected that consumers will play an active role in the design process of their products, while producers will focus on the most successful designs. Co-creation processes, production tools, advertising networks, as well as a sustainable, social, and economic approach will need to be changed in order to achieve this goal.

Given this new scenario, we can raise some questions that will be a future challenge: what is needed to encourage more prosumers? How many people would be willing to change their consumption habits? In the current market, what motivations can encourage co-creation? What can consumers do to contribute to research?

There is a need to work on these issues from the viewpoints of both research and industry in order to increase the presence of prosumers in the marketplace and in society. Cooperation must be achieved in a way that provides benefits to all parties. Methods and strategies must be proposed in order to achieve this.

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